

Citizens facing the (in)communication of blackouts

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The government of Ecuador, faced with power shortages, must communicate the crisis in order to 'minimise damage, maintain public confidence and guide appropriate actions and responses to the emergency'. However, citizens are trying to identify the right channels and spokespersons to take the correct guidelines.

The often unnoticed changes in blackout schedules cause unease. Many leaders have expressed dissatisfaction because activities cannot be planned. Explanations are demanded, but there is a feeling of electoral opportunism, and President Noboa himself said that he is unaware of the criteria issued by the technicians.

In this scenario, without consistent and systematic official messaging, it is up to citizens to promote appropriate networks and formats to mitigate and overcome the limitations of electricity shortages.

Neighbourhood chats, messages between family members and conversations between acquaintances are effective in decrypting the 'official' pages of electricity distribution companies. It happens that a 'meme', a graphic or an audio produced by neighbours is more accurate than the portentous public propaganda, because the former seeks to communicate, to forge collaborative actions, while the latter tries to sell a candidate.

Social communication is bidirectional, it is creating spaces for meeting and working together on the basis of codes, languages and meanings that are understood by senders and receivers, it translates into consensus and multiple contributions.

Part of the solutions will emerge from honest dialogues between citizens and decision-makers, the first step being to strengthen and advance secure crisis communication.